

Standard Bases in Local Rings

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Abstract

Gröbner bases provide a systematic way to handle polynomial ideals in algebraic geometry and computer algebra. However, these methods rely on global term orders that fail in local settings such as formal power series rings or localizations. In this article we introduce *standard bases*, a natural extension of Gröbner bases to local rings, and explain how they allow computations “near a point” on an algebraic variety. We discuss the key theoretical results—including a local version of Buchberger’s criterion and a dimension theorem—and describe Mora’s algorithm for computing standard bases. Several examples illustrate how the theory can be used to study local properties of algebraic varieties.

Note. This manuscript is an *expository paper* following the presentation of Cox, Little, and O’Shea (2005), intended as a learning resource for readers encountering standard bases in local rings for the first time.

1 Introduction

Gröbner bases have revolutionized computational algebraic geometry by providing an algorithmic approach to ideals in polynomial rings. They make it possible to perform operations such as elimination, intersection, and ideal membership checks entirely by symbolic computation; see, for instance, [1, 2].

Yet the usual Gröbner basis theory is inherently *global*: it views polynomials as algebraic functions over the entire affine space. In many geometric problems, we are interested in the behavior of an algebraic variety *near a single point*—for instance, in studying a singularity or performing a local expansion. To work “locally,” we pass from the polynomial ring $k[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ to one of its localizations or completions, such as

$$R = k[x_1, \dots, x_n]_{(x_1, \dots, x_n)} \quad \text{or} \quad R = k[[x_1, \dots, x_n]].$$

In this new environment, the familiar tools of Gröbner bases no longer apply without modification: local rings are not well-ordered, so the standard division algorithm may fail to terminate. Nevertheless, the underlying geometric motivation—to describe ideals in terms of their leading terms—remains the same.

The theory of *standard bases*, introduced by Teo Mora in the 1980s [3], extends the Gröbner basis philosophy to local rings. The idea is to replace ordinary division with *Mora’s normal form algorithm*, which behaves well in the absence of a well-order. This leads to a local version of *Buchberger’s criterion*, providing an effective method to compute standard bases, and to a *dimension theorem* that connects algebraic and combinatorial data in the local setting.

Standard bases have since become an essential tool in computational algebraic geometry, especially in the study of singularities and local intersection theory. In this article we give an expository introduction to their theory, following the presentation in Cox, Little, and O’Shea’s *Using Algebraic Geometry* [1], but with expanded explanations and examples aimed at readers familiar with Gröbner bases who wish to understand their local analogs.

Section 2 recalls the concept of local orders and standard bases. Section 3 explains Mora’s normal form algorithm and the local version of Buchberger’s criterion. Section 4 presents the dimension theorem for local rings and its interpretation in terms of standard monomials. Section 5 discusses applications to ideal membership, elimination, and ideal operations, with an example illustrating the theory.

2 Local orders and standard bases

Throughout, k denotes a field, and we write $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ for a list of variables. We begin by recalling the notion of a semigroup order and then specialize to local orders.

2.1 Semigroup orders

Let \mathbb{N}^n be the additive semigroup of exponent vectors. A *semigroup order* on \mathbb{N}^n is a total order $>$ such that:

- (i) $>$ is compatible with addition: if $\alpha > \beta$ then $\alpha + \gamma > \beta + \gamma$ for all $\gamma \in \mathbb{N}^n$;
- (ii) $>$ is a well-partial-order when restricted to any finite subset of \mathbb{N}^n .

Using the identification $x^\alpha = x_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots x_n^{\alpha_n}$, a semigroup order on \mathbb{N}^n induces an order on monomials.

Definition 2.1. A semigroup order $>$ on monomials is called *global* if 1 is the smallest monomial, and it is called *local* if 1 is the largest monomial. Equivalently, $>$ is local if $x^\alpha > 1$ implies $|\alpha| < 0$, which can only happen if degrees are ordered in reverse.

In practice, we often require compatibility with degree.

Definition 2.2. A term order $>$ is called *degree-antcompatible* if

$$|\alpha| > |\beta| \implies x^\alpha < x^\beta$$

for all $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{N}^n$. A typical example is the negative graded lexicographic or negative graded reverse lexicographic order, in which higher degree monomials are considered *smaller*.

Intuitively, a local order behaves as follows: monomials of higher degree are *farther away from the origin* and are therefore smaller. This aligns with the idea of working locally near the maximal ideal (x_1, \dots, x_n) , where high-degree terms are regarded as “negligible” in comparison with low-degree ones.

2.2 Local rings of interest

The local theory of standard bases is usually developed in one of the following rings:

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 &= k[x_1, \dots, x_n]_{(x_1, \dots, x_n)}, \\ R_2 &= k[[x_1, \dots, x_n]], \\ R_3 &= k\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}, \end{aligned}$$

where $k\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ denotes convergent power series when $k \subseteq \mathbb{C}$. In each case, the maximal ideal is generated by x_1, \dots, x_n and consists of all elements without constant term. The ring R_1 is the localization of the polynomial ring at this maximal ideal, R_2 is the formal power series ring, and R_3 is the ring of convergent power series.

Remark 2.3. For the purposes of standard bases, these three settings behave very similarly: they are Noetherian, complete with respect to the \mathfrak{m} -adic topology, and their ideals can be described by finitely many generators with well-defined leading terms relative to a chosen local order.

2.3 Leading terms and standard bases

Fix a local order $>$ on monomials. Every nonzero $f \in R_i$ can be written as

$$f = \sum_{\alpha} c_{\alpha} x^{\alpha}, \quad c_{\alpha} \in k,$$

where the sum extends over a subset of \mathbb{N}^n . Since $>$ is total, there is a unique largest monomial appearing with nonzero coefficient.

Definition 2.4. Let $f \in R_i$ be nonzero. The *leading term* $\text{LT}(f)$ is the monomial $c_{\alpha} x^{\alpha}$ with largest x^{α} with respect to $>$ among those appearing in f , including its coefficient. The *leading monomial* $\text{LM}(f)$ is just the monomial x^{α} , and the *leading coefficient* is c_{α} .

If $I \subset R_i$ is an ideal, the set of leading monomials of elements of I generates a monomial ideal.

Definition 2.5. Let $I \subset R_i$ be an ideal. The *leading term ideal* of I is

$$\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle := \langle \text{LT}(f) : f \in I \rangle \subset R_i.$$

Similarly, the *leading monomial ideal* $\langle \text{LM}(I) \rangle$ is generated by all $\text{LM}(f)$ with $f \in I$.

Just as in the polynomial case, it is desirable to describe $\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle$ using the leading terms of finitely many generators of I .

Definition 2.6. Let $I \subset R_i$ be a nonzero ideal and let $G = \{g_1, \dots, g_t\} \subset I$ be a finite subset. We say that G is a *standard basis* of I (with respect to $>$) if

$$\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle = \langle \text{LT}(g_1), \dots, \text{LT}(g_t) \rangle.$$

The existence of standard bases in these local rings follows from Noetherian arguments analogous to the polynomial case.

Proposition 2.7. *Every nonzero ideal I in R_1, R_2 or R_3 admits a finite standard basis with respect to any fixed local order $>$.*

Idea of proof. Consider the set of leading term ideals $\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle$. As R_i is Noetherian, the set of monomial ideals is well-founded with respect to inclusion (ascending chain condition). Choose elements g_1, g_2, \dots in I such that their leading monomials generate $\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle$ minimally. By Noetherianity, a finite subcollection suffices, say g_1, \dots, g_t . Then $G = \{g_1, \dots, g_t\}$ has the desired property. A more detailed argument is given, for instance, in [2]. \square

3 Mora’s normal form algorithm and Buchberger’s criterion

In the polynomial case, Gröbner bases are characterized in terms of the multivariate division algorithm. In local rings, ordinary division may not terminate because a local order need not be a well-order: one can have infinite descending chains of monomials. Mora’s algorithm replaces the division algorithm by a more subtle procedure that still yields a meaningful *normal form* for reduction by a finite set.

3.1 Intuition

Suppose $G = \{g_1, \dots, g_t\}$ is a finite subset of R_i . We want to reduce a given f by G in such a way that at each step we cancel a leading term of f using the leading terms of the g_j , but we must avoid infinite descent. The key idea of Mora’s algorithm is to allow some “backtracking” in the order and to control the sequence of reductions so that eventually the process stabilizes when G is a standard basis.

3.2 Mora normal form

We will not give a fully formal algorithmic description here, but rather summarize the essential properties.

Definition 3.1. Let $G \subset R_i$ be finite and $f \in R_i$. A *Mora normal form* of f with respect to G , denoted $\text{NF}_{\text{Mora}}(f, G)$, is an element $r \in R_i$ such that

$$f = \sum_{j=1}^t a_j g_j + r, \quad a_j \in R_i,$$

and no term of r is divisible by any $\text{LM}(g_j)$. In addition, the algorithm producing r uses only finitely many reduction steps, provided G is a standard basis.

The crucial property is that Mora normal forms behave well with respect to ideal membership when G is a standard basis.

Proposition 3.2. Let $I = \langle G \rangle \subset R_i$ and assume G is a standard basis of I . Then for $f \in R_i$,

$$\text{NF}_{\text{Mora}}(f, G) = 0 \iff f \in I.$$

Sketch. If $f \in I$ and G is a standard basis, the leading terms of f can always be cancelled by leading terms of elements of G , as in the polynomial case. Mora’s algorithm is designed to exploit this and to terminate after finitely many steps; thus we end with remainder 0. Conversely, if $\text{NF}_{\text{Mora}}(f, G) = 0$ then by definition f lies in the ideal generated by the g_j . A detailed treatment can be found in [3, 2]. \square

3.3 Local Buchberger criterion

We now present the local analog of Buchberger’s criterion. We start with a set $S \subset k[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ and consider the ideal it generates in a suitable localization.

Let $>$ be a semigroup order on $k[x_1, \dots, x_n]$, which we use to define a localization

$$R = \text{Loc}_{>}(k[x_1, \dots, x_n]),$$

obtained by inverting all polynomials whose leading term is 1 (or whose leading monomial is 1). Then R is a local ring with maximal ideal generated by those variables x_i that are larger than 1 in the order.

Let $S = \{g_1, \dots, g_t\} \subset k[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ and let I be the ideal in R generated by S . As in the global case, we can form S -polynomials:

Definition 3.3. For $g_i, g_j \in S$ with leading terms $\text{LT}(g_i), \text{LT}(g_j)$, the S -polynomial is

$$S(g_i, g_j) = \frac{\text{lcm}(\text{LM}(g_i), \text{LM}(g_j))}{\text{LT}(g_i)} g_i - \frac{\text{lcm}(\text{LM}(g_i), \text{LM}(g_j))}{\text{LT}(g_j)} g_j.$$

Theorem 3.4 (Buchberger's criterion for local rings). *Let $S = \{g_1, \dots, g_t\} \subset k[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ and let I be the ideal in $R = \text{Loc}_{>}(k[x_1, \dots, x_n])$ generated by S . Then the following are equivalent:*

- (a) S is a standard basis of I with respect to the induced local order;
- (b) For every pair i, j , the Mora normal form of the S -polynomial $S(g_i, g_j)$ with respect to S is zero:

$$\text{NF}_{\text{Mora}}(S(g_i, g_j), S) = 0.$$

Idea of the proof. The proof follows the same general pattern as the global Buchberger criterion, but extra care is needed because the order is not a well-order.

(a) \Rightarrow (b): Assume S is a standard basis. Then in particular $\text{LT}(I)$ is generated by $\text{LT}(g_1), \dots, \text{LT}(g_t)$. Each $S(g_i, g_j)$ lies in I , so its leading term is in $\langle \text{LT}(S) \rangle$. Thus the Mora reduction process (which mimics the cancellation of leading terms) eventually cancels all terms of $S(g_i, g_j)$, giving remainder zero.

(b) \Rightarrow (a): For the converse, one shows that under the hypothesis that all S -polynomials reduce to zero, every $f \in I$ can be written in such a way that its leading term lies in the ideal generated by leading terms of the g_j . One considers all possible representations

$$f = \sum_{j=1}^t a_j g_j, \quad a_j \in R,$$

and defines a set of possible leading terms analogous to the set S_f in [1]. Using the vanishing of S -polynomials, one can systematically rewrite f to reduce its minimal possible leading term, eventually forcing that leading term to be in $\langle \text{LT}(S) \rangle$. This shows that $\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle = \langle \text{LT}(S) \rangle$, so S is a standard basis. \square

3.4 Buchberger–Mora algorithm and termination

The previous theorem suggests an algorithm for computing a standard basis starting from any finite generating set S .

Theorem 3.5 (Buchberger–Mora algorithm). *Let $S \subset k[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ be finite and let $>$ be a semi-group order. Then there is an algorithm, obtained by modifying Buchberger's algorithm to use Mora normal forms, which computes a standard basis of the ideal I in $R = \text{Loc}_{>}(k[x_1, \dots, x_n])$ generated by S . The algorithm terminates after finitely many steps.*

Idea of the proof. The algorithm proceeds as follows: starting with $G_0 = S$, repeatedly consider pairs (g_i, g_j) in G_k , compute their S -polynomial, reduce it using Mora's algorithm with respect to G_k , and if the remainder $r \neq 0$, adjoin r to the basis to form G_{k+1} . The key point is to show that this process cannot go on indefinitely.

Termination is proved using the ascending chain condition (ACC) on monomial ideals. At each step the leading term ideal $\langle \text{LT}(G_k) \rangle$ strictly increases when a new element is added. By ACC, the chain

$$\langle \text{LT}(G_0) \rangle \subseteq \langle \text{LT}(G_1) \rangle \subseteq \cdots$$

stabilizes after finitely many steps, so the algorithm eventually stops. When it stops, all S -polynomials reduce to zero, and by Theorem 3.4 the final set G is a standard basis. \square

4 A dimension theorem for local rings

We now discuss a dimension theorem in terms of standard monomials, generalizing a classical result from the global Gröbner basis theory.

4.1 Standard monomials

Let R be one of the local rings R_1, R_2, R_3 introduced earlier, and let $I \subset R$ be an ideal. The monomial ideal $\langle \text{LM}(I) \rangle$ decomposes the set of all monomials into those which lie in the ideal and those which do not.

Definition 4.1. A monomial x^α is called *standard* for I (with respect to $>$) if $x^\alpha \notin \langle \text{LM}(I) \rangle$. The set of standard monomials is denoted by

$$\mathcal{B} = \{x^\alpha : x^\alpha \notin \langle \text{LM}(I) \rangle\}.$$

Intuitively, \mathcal{B} is a monomial basis of the quotient R/I whenever this quotient is finite-dimensional as a k -vector space.

4.2 Statement of the theorem

Theorem 4.2 (Dimension theorem for local rings). *Let R be one of $k[x_1, \dots, x_n]_{(x_1, \dots, x_n)}$, $k[[x_1, \dots, x_n]]$ or $k\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, and let $I \subset R$ be an ideal. The following are equivalent:*

- (a) *The quotient R/I is finite-dimensional as a k -vector space.*
- (b) *The quotient $R/\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle$ is finite-dimensional as a k -vector space.*
- (c) *There are only finitely many standard monomials for I .*

Moreover, when these conditions hold, we have

$$\dim_k(R/I) = \dim_k(R/\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle) = \#\mathcal{B},$$

and every $f \in R$ can be uniquely written as

$$f = g + \sum c_\alpha x^\alpha,$$

with $g \in I$, $c_\alpha \in k$, and the sum taken over standard monomials.

4.3 Proof

We sketch the main steps.

(a) \Rightarrow (c)

Assume $\dim_k(R/I)$ is finite. Suppose, to the contrary, that there are infinitely many standard monomials. Then we can choose distinct monomials $x^{\alpha_1}, x^{\alpha_2}, \dots$ such that none lies in $\langle \text{LM}(I) \rangle$. Their images in R/I would then give infinitely many linearly independent classes, contradicting the finiteness of $\dim_k(R/I)$. Hence (c) holds.

(c) \Rightarrow (a)

Assume that \mathcal{B} , the set of standard monomials, is finite. Let $G = \{g_1, \dots, g_t\}$ be a standard basis of I . We claim that the residue classes of elements of \mathcal{B} form a k -basis of R/I .

Given $f \in R$, we apply Mora's algorithm to reduce f with respect to G . One obtains a decomposition

$$f = g_1 + h_1, \quad g_1 \in I,$$

where h_1 is either zero or has $\text{LT}(h_1) \notin \langle \text{LT}(G) \rangle$. Writing

$$h_1 = c_1 x^{\alpha_1} + r_1$$

with x^{α_1} a monomial and $\text{LT}(r_1) < \text{LT}(h_1)$, we get

$$f = g_1 + c_1 x^{\alpha_1} + r_1.$$

If $r_1 \neq 0$ we repeat the process, obtaining

$$r_1 = g_2 + h_2, \quad h_2 = c_2 x^{\alpha_2} + r_2, \text{ etc.}$$

Each time, the leading term strictly decreases, so the sequence of leading monomials $\text{LM}(h_i)$ forms a strictly descending chain in the local order. Since every monomial is eventually smaller than any fixed finite subset, the process cannot go on indefinitely if there are only finitely many standard monomials. In other words, the reduction process terminates after finitely many steps and produces a representation

$$f = g + \sum_{\alpha \in A} c_\alpha x^\alpha,$$

where $g \in I$ and each x^α is standard. This shows that the cosets of standard monomials span R/I as a k -vector space. Linear independence is proved as usual: if a linear combination of standard monomials lies in I , its leading term would be in $\langle \text{LM}(I) \rangle$, contradicting standardness.

Thus the images of \mathcal{B} form a basis of R/I , and $\dim_k(R/I) = \#\mathcal{B}$.

(b) \Leftrightarrow (c)

The quotient $R/\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle$ has a natural monomial basis given by monomials not in $\langle \text{LM}(I) \rangle$, i.e. by standard monomials. Therefore, the dimension of $R/\langle \text{LT}(I) \rangle$ equals the number of standard monomials. This shows (b) \Leftrightarrow (c). Combining the implications yields the entire theorem.

5 Applications

We briefly describe some applications of standard bases in local rings. The statements mirror well-known results in the global Gröbner basis theory, but their proofs rely on the local machinery developed above.

5.1 Ideal membership

Let $I \subset R$ be an ideal and G a standard basis of I . Then for any $f \in R$, ideal membership can be tested by reduction:

Proposition 5.1 (Ideal membership). *Let R be as in Theorem 4.2, $I \subset R$ an ideal, and G a standard basis of I . Then*

$$f \in I \iff \text{NF}_{\text{Mora}}(f, G) = 0.$$

This is the local analog of the familiar global membership test using Gröbner bases, but now with Mora normal form instead of the usual division algorithm.

5.2 Local elimination

We next consider elimination in a local context. Let

$$S = R[t] = k[x_1, \dots, x_n]_{(x_1, \dots, x_n)}[t].$$

Given an ideal $J \subset S$, we define its elimination ideal

$$J_0 = J \cap R,$$

consisting of all elements of J that do not involve t .

Theorem 5.2 (Local elimination). *Let $J \subset S$ be an ideal. Choose an elimination order $>_{\text{elim}}$ on the monomials in x_1, \dots, x_n, t such that powers of t are considered larger than any monomials in the x_i , and on the x_i we use a fixed local order $>$. Compute a standard basis G of J with respect to $>_{\text{elim}}$. Then*

$$G_0 = G \cap R = \{g \in G : \text{LT}(g) \text{ does not contain } t\}$$

is a standard basis of J_0 with respect to the local order on R .

Idea. The proof is parallel to the global elimination theorem for Gröbner bases, see [1]. The elimination order ensures that leading terms involving t cannot be cancelled by terms without t , so the monomial ideal of J_0 is generated by the leading terms of those $g \in G$ that do not involve t . A careful argument shows that this set indeed generates $\text{LT}(J_0)$, hence G_0 is a standard basis of J_0 . \square

5.3 Ideal operations

Standard bases can also be used to compute operations such as intersection and quotients of ideals in local rings. We just state the guiding formulas.

Intersection

Let $I, J \subset R$. Direct computation of $I \cap J$ is usually difficult. Introduce a new variable t and consider the ideal

$$K = tI + (1 - t)J \subset R[t].$$

Then one has

$$I \cap J = K \cap R.$$

Thus $I \cap J$ can be computed using local elimination (Theorem 5.2) applied to K .

Quotients and stable quotients

Let $I \subset R$ be an ideal and $f \in R$. The *colon ideal*

$$I : \langle f \rangle = \{g \in R : fg \in I\}$$

can be expressed as

$$I : \langle f \rangle = \frac{1}{f}(I \cap \langle f \rangle),$$

and the latter can again be treated via intersection and elimination.

The *stable quotient*

$$I : f^\infty = \{g \in R : f^n g \in I \text{ for some } n \geq 1\}$$

admits the representation

$$I : f^\infty = (I + \langle 1 - ft \rangle) \cap R \subset R[t].$$

Again, this turns the stable quotient into an elimination problem.

Radical membership

Finally, membership in the radical \sqrt{I} of an ideal I can be tested by:

$$f \in \sqrt{I} \iff 1 \in I + \langle 1 - ft \rangle \subset R[t].$$

The right-hand side can be checked using a standard basis of $I + \langle 1 - ft \rangle$ with respect to a suitable local elimination order.

6 Example

We conclude with a worked example illustrating the dimension theorem and giving a flavor of computations with standard bases.

Example 6.1. Let $R = k[x, y]_{(x, y)}$ and consider the ideal

$$I = \langle y^2 - x^3, xy - x^4 \rangle \subset R.$$

Geometrically, I describes a singular curve germ at the origin. We choose a local order in which $x > y$ and which is degree-anticompatible, e.g. negative degree lexicographic with $x > y$.

Using the Buchberger–Mora algorithm (or a computer algebra system such as SINGULAR), one finds that a standard basis of I is given by

$$G = \{g_1, g_2, g_3\} = \{y^2 - x^3, xy - x^4, y^3 - x^5\}.$$

The leading monomials (with respect to the chosen order) are

$$\text{LM}(g_1) = y^2, \quad \text{LM}(g_2) = xy, \quad \text{LM}(g_3) = y^3.$$

Hence the leading monomial ideal is

$$\langle \text{LM}(I) \rangle = \langle y^2, xy \rangle.$$

The standard monomials are those not divisible by y^2 or xy . A quick inspection shows that the standard monomials up to the relevant degree are

$$1, x, y, x^2, xy,$$

and in fact one can verify that the full set of standard monomials is

$$\mathcal{B} = \{1, x, y, x^2, xy\}.$$

Therefore

$$\dim_k(R/I) = \#\mathcal{B} = 5.$$

This agrees with the intuition that R/I is an Artinian local ring of length 5, encoding the multiplicity of the singular point. The example thus illustrates Theorem 4.2.

7 Concluding remarks

Standard bases extend the powerful machinery of Gröbner bases to local and analytic settings. They rely on local term orders and the Mora normal form algorithm, but the structural results closely parallel those in the global theory:

- Buchberger’s criterion for standard bases provides an algorithmic characterization via vanishing of S -polynomials.
- The Buchberger–Mora algorithm computes standard bases and terminates thanks to the ascending chain condition on monomial ideals.
- The dimension theorem expresses the dimension (or length) of a local quotient in terms of standard monomials.
- Applications to ideal membership, elimination and ideal operations make standard bases a practical tool in computational local algebra and singularity theory.

From a computational viewpoint, many of these algorithms are implemented in modern computer algebra systems, for instance in SINGULAR and MACAULAY2, where local orderings and standard bases can be used to study curve and surface singularities and to perform local computations on varieties.

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